

FOUR WETTING PHASES IN AlN/Al AND AlN+C/Al SYSTEMS.

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ABSTRACT

The improved sessile drop technique was used to measure the changes in contact angle between molten aluminum and each of AlN and a composite AlN+C. By plotting the results on a logarithmic time scale, it was found that the contact angle value for normal AlN (containing sintering agents) progresses through four phases (I: dynamic non-equilibrium, II: quasi-equilibrium, III: chemical non-equilibrium, IV: equilibrium), while the value for purified AlN progresses through only two phases, I and IV (or II). The wetting in phase III (interfacial-reaction wetting) was caused by the production of Al_2O_3 at the interface. The contact angle value in phase IV (equilibrium wettability) is dependent on the results of the interfacial reactions. For AlN+C composites, the contact angle also progresses through four phases. The contact angle of phase II (original wettability) conforms to Cassie's law, whereas the contact angle of phase IV resembles the phase IV contact angle of the reactive component of the composite. The production of Al_3C_4 at the interface causes each contact angle to be similar. These new observations suggest that a decrease in the total energy of the system is the driving force for contact angle decrease.

KEYWORDS: Wetting; Wettability; Aluminum; Aluminum nitride; Interfacial reaction.

1. INTRODUCTION

The wetting and the wettability of a ceramic surface by a molten metal have long been a subject of study^{(1) - (5)} and are important factors

whenever a molten metal is used. In a reactive system, interfacial reactions often change the degree of wetting over time and have led many researchers to misinterpret the wetting and the wettability. The authors made the new discovery that the wetting in a reactive system progresses through three distinct phases (I: dynamic non-equilibrium, II: quasi-equilibrium, III: chemical non-equilibrium) ⁽⁶⁾ ⁽⁷⁾ and suggested that the original wetting occurred during phase I ⁽⁸⁾ and the original wettability could be measured only during phase II ⁽⁹⁾.

This paper presents, as the following step, the findings of a study regarding wetting in a non-reactive and a composite system. For this purpose, the contact angles of molten aluminum for two kinds of AlN and pure Al₂O₃ as models of the non-reactive system for 60mass% AlN + 40mass% C (AlN as a non-reactive component and carbon as a reactive component) as a model of the composite system were measured by the improved sessile drop method which minimized the oxidation of aluminum. These new observations allow us to more clearly understand the relationship between wetting and interfacial reactions and clarify the dynamical and chemical condition of each wetting phase.

2. EXPERIMENTAL APPARATUS AND PROCEDURE

2.1 Improved sessile drop method apparatus A schematic diagram of the system devised for the sessile drop method ⁽⁷⁾ ⁽⁹⁾ is shown in Figure 1(a). The system consists of a sealed chamber, a purification system for the atmospheric gas (He + 3%H₂) in the chamber, a set of vacuum pumps to evacuate the chamber, two light sources, and two cameras (a 35 mm camera

FIGURE 1 (a). Improved sessile drop method apparatus.

(b). Al dropping device.

and a video recording camera both with bellows and macro lenses). The sealed chamber has four windows and contains a molten aluminum dropping device. The gas purification system⁽⁵⁾ consists of an oxygen trap, two liquid nitrogen cold traps and a sponge titanium furnace heated to about 1073K to remove oxygen and water from the atmospheric gas, so that oxidation of the aluminum surface is minimized.

As shown in Figure 1(b), the aluminum dropping device is a tube of pure alumina (99.8 mass%) with a 1mm diameter hole in its base. Immediately after the aluminum pellet is melted and heated to the experimental temperature, it is slowly forced through the hole in the base of the tube by gradually and slightly decreasing the atmospheric pressure of the chamber. This method has four distinct advantages as mentioned in our previous paper⁽⁹⁾.

2.2 Materials The experiments were conducted using 99.99 mass% aluminum pellets as the metal. The aluminum pellets weighed approximately 70mg each and were preheated by immersion in hydrofluoric acid and then in acetone. As the substrate, two kinds of AlN, 99.9 mass% Al₂O₃ and a composite AlN+C were used. The AlN samples specifically differ from each other in their contents of oxygen and yttrium as shown in Table 1.

Table 1 Yttrium and Oxygen Contents in each AlN (mass%)

Sample	Y	O
AlN-A	0.11	0.30
AlN-B	4.1	2.0

When AlN is sintered, yttrium compounds or calcium compounds, for example Y₂O₃ or CaO⁽¹⁰⁾, is often used as a sintering agent since AlN is difficult to sinter. Though these chemical compounds allow AlN to attain a high density and conductivity, they make the AlN impure (AlN-B). The authors succeeded in producing purified AlN (AlN-A). The method consists of removing the yttrium compounds by heating each sample in a nitrogen atmosphere containing CO₂ at 2173K for 30 hours and then by hydrolyzing in air⁽¹¹⁾. The original sample of AlN was sintered using a yttrium compound in a nitrogen atmosphere at 2073K for two hours. Each AlN has the dimensions of 30φmm x 5mm. The Al₂O₃, manufactured by Asahikasei Industry Co., Ltd., has the dimensions of 20mm x 20mm x 0.25mm. The AlN+C composite material contains 60mass% AlN and 40mass% C. Sixty percent of the carbon was derived from granular carbon and 40% was derived from the binder. The carbon from the granular carbon was graphite, while the carbon from the

binder was in an amorphous state. The contact angles for pure AlN and pure carbon were measured and used as standards. The contact angles of the composite were compared to them. The pure carbon sample consisted of non-crystallized carbon, whereas the composite contained graphite and amorphous carbon. It is believed this difference only has a small effect on the wetting.

These sintered ceramic plates were polished to a mirror finish using various grades of SiC paper and two grades of diamond paste (particle diameter $6\mu\text{m}$ and $0.25\mu\text{m}$). Before the experiments, the plates were cleaned in acetone using an ultrasonic cleaner.

2.3 Experimental Procedure A ceramic plate was set in a horizontal position under the dropping device before the chamber was evacuated to $1.3 \times 10^{-3} \text{Pa}$ (approximately 10^{-5} Torr) and heated to 1423K. This temperature was maintained for about 1200s. The plate was then allowed to cool to 1073K, at which point the purified He+3% H_2 atmospheric gas was introduced and the pressure raised to 120kPa (1.2atm). The chamber was then reheated and when the plate reached 1373K, the aluminum pellet was inserted into the dropping device. Immediately after the aluminum pellet was melted and heated to the experimental temperature, it was slowly sucked through the hole in the base of the tube by gradually and slightly decreasing the atmospheric pressure of the chamber. The rate of dropping is thus minimized and the gas flow due to the difference in pressure between the chamber and the tube stops as soon as the drop passes through the hole. The slow drop rate maximizes the possibility of obtaining an advancing or equilibrium contact angle instead of a receding one.

When a receding contact angle did result, the value was disregarded and the experiment repeated. The sessile drop was photographed after five seconds, ten seconds, and then at ten second intervals up to 60s and finally at intermittently increasing intervals until the end of the drop cycle (7.2ks). Right and left hand contact angles θ were measured using projections of the 35mm monochrome negatives (magnification 50x). When θ was less than 90° , it could be measured directly on the projections but when θ was greater than 90° , it was calculated using Bashforth and Adams' tables^(1,2). The video camera was used to film the early behavior of the sessile drops and to provide a cross reference for the contact angle. If the contact angles recorded by the two cameras differed by more than a few degrees or if the bulk drop was unsymmetrical then the results of the drop cycle were disregarded and the experiment was repeated.

3. Experimental Results and Discussion

3.1 Wetting of AlN

Figure 2 compares the contact angle curve for AlN-B with the curves for AlN-A and Al_2O_3 . The value of the contact angle for the AlN-A is constant, as it is for the Al_2O_3 , but much larger. The contact angle value for AlN-B (containing Y_2O_3) decreases over time through three wetting phases (I,II,III) similar to that for MgO, a typical reactive system^{(7) (9)} and then shows a fourth phase (equilibrium phase). Phase I (vibratory phase) occurred within 5s after dropping and is not shown in Figure 2. On the contrary, the contact angle value for AlN-A is constant and does not have phases II and III. The phase II contact angle value for AlN-B is slightly lower than that for AlN-A, while significant differences were produced in phases III and IV⁽⁹⁾. The existence of phases II and III depends on the quantity of impurities in the ceramic plate. These results also indicate that phase III and IV were caused by the interfacial reaction.

FIGURE 2. Contact angle curves for AlN and Al_2O_3 at 1373 K
(AlN-A: purified AlN, AlN-B: AlN containing Y_2O_3).

The secondary electron image and the results of three EPMA analyses for the interfacial reaction zone of AlN-B are shown in Figure 3. It was confirmed that the chemical reaction produced a new product towards the molten aluminum, and oxygen exists in the place of nitrogen in the new product. Using a microdiffractometer, it was confirmed that the product was $\alpha-Al_2O_3$. In contrast, yttrium was not found in the reaction zone but was detected in the aluminum. Therefore, the reaction formula is expressed as follows:

These results prove that the phase IV contact angle value for AlN-B is similar to that for the Al_2O_3 .

FIGURE 3. X-ray mapping of reaction zone for AlN-B (1373 K, 7200 s).

3.2 Wetting of AlN+C Figure 4 shows the curve of the contact angle between AlN+C and molten aluminum at 1373K compared with the curves of the purified AlN (AlN-A) and the pure carbon. The contact angle curve for AlN+C has four phases similar to those for MgO ^{(7) (9)} and the impure AlN (AlN-B) samples. The value of the phase II contact angle for AlN+C will be between that for pure AlN and pure carbon. Assuming the contact angle follows Cassie's equation^{(13) (14)}, the contact angle for AlN+C is calculated as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}\theta_{AlN+C} &= \arccos(A_{AlN} \cos \theta_{AlN} + A_C \cos \theta_C) \\ &= \arccos(0.6 \cos 128^\circ + 0.4 \cos 106^\circ) \\ &= 119^\circ\end{aligned}$$

where A_x is the ratio of the area of X on the surface and θ_x is the contact angle for pure X. The measured value for AlN from the present study is approximately 116° , which is within the experimental error range. The results strengthen the hypothesis that the phase II contact angle

wettability). In contrast, the phase IV contact angles for the composite, resemble the phase IV contact angles for the pure carbon. It is postulated that the area of Al_4C_3 , which is produced at the interface, gets larger and larger since the production of Al_4C_3 reduces the total energy of the system. This is believed to be the reason for the similarity of the contact angles. In general the phase IV contact angle for a composite material will be similar to the contact angle for the component whose contact angle is lowest. This result suggests that a decrease in the total energy of the system is the driving force for the contact angle decrease.

FIGURE 4. Contact angle curves for AlN+40 mass% C, AlN-A and C at 1373 K.

4. SUMMARY

The changes in contact angles of aluminum for one kind of Al_2O_3 and two kinds of AlN: purified AlN, AlN containing Y_2O_3 as models of non-reactive systems and AlN+C (60mass% AlN as a non-reactive component and 40mass% C as a reactive component) as a model of composite materials were measured using the improved sessile drop method which minimized the oxidation of aluminum.

(1) The contact angle for a normal AlN (including Y_2O_3 as a sintering agent) has the following four phases.

- I: dynamical non-equilibrium phase
- II: quasi-equilibrium phase
- III: chemical non-equilibrium phase
- IV: equilibrium phase

(2) The contact angles for both pure Al_2O_3 and purified AlN have only two

phases and do not progress through phases II and III. The phase IV (or II) contact angle between purified AlN and molten aluminum was found to be approximately 128° (at 1373K), which was higher than that found for pure Al_2O_3 (89° at 1373K).

(3) The interfacial-reaction wetting (phase III) is caused by the production of $\alpha\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ at the interface toward the molten aluminum and the equilibrium wettability (phase IV) depends on the results of the interfacial reactions.

(4) There are also four phases for the contact angles for a composite material accompanied by the production of Al_4C_3 at the interface.

(5) The phase II contact angle value (original wettability) in a composite system follows Cassie's equation, while the phase IV contact value (equilibrium wettability) in a composite system resembles the contact angle for the component which has better wettability.

(6) These results suggest that a decrease in the total energy of the system is the driving force for contact angle decrease.

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